

Orchestrator

– User Manual –

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1. Introduction

The *Orchestrator* is a central component of the MEDINA framework and processes and stores all evidence and assessment results. It receives them from the evidence collection and security assessment tools, and forwards them to the appropriate components, such as the *Continuous Certificated Evaluation*¹ (CCE). Furthermore, it provides a database that stores evidence and assessment results, as well as metrics, and other data.

Via its graphical user interface, the *Orchestrator* additionally provides users with multiple possibilities to review and manage cloud services, metrics, and many other information.

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to *the Orchestrator* is managed by Keycloak². The operations that are allowed to be carried out are conditioned by the role to which each authenticated user is assigned. The cloud services that are shown are filtered according to the read permissions by the authenticated user. Similarly, the certificates are filtered. The Metrics and Catalogues views, however, are not filtered.

¹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

² <https://www.keycloak.org>

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

The *Orchestrator* offers four main views: Cloud Services, Metrics, Catalogues, and Certificates (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The four main views of the Orchestrator UI

2.2. Cloud Services

The Cloud Services view is the main view of the *Orchestrator* UI. It first presents an overview of existing cloud services and the possibility to create a new one.

- **Creating a new cloud service:** To create a new cloud service click on the *Add service* button and enter a name and description. Then click on *Save*. This will save the new service in the *Orchestrator*.
- **Creating a new Target of Evaluation:** Creating a new cloud service does not trigger its evaluation. To trigger its evaluation for a certain certification schema, a Target of Evaluation (ToE) must be created. To do so, click on a cloud service and navigate to the Configuration tab (see Figure 2). Within the Configuration tab, click on Target of Evaluation and select the desired certification schema and assurance level.
- **Deleting a cloud service or ToE:** To delete a cloud service or ToE, navigate to the respective overview and click on the red button (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Overview of an individual cloud service

Additionally, to the configuration options described above, multiple tabs within a cloud service present information about resources, metrics, and assessment results. The Discovery tab shows which resources have been discovered for the service (see Figure 3). The Metrics tab presents similar information to the Metrics view described in Section 2.3, but filtered for the respective cloud service. Finally, the Assessment tab shows the assessment results that have been submitted related to that cloud service (see Figure 4).

Figure 3. The Discovery overview of a cloud service which shows the resources that have been discovered. The "Show more info" button reveals more detailed information about the resource

Figure 4. The Assessment tab of a cloud service. It allows to filter the assessment results for various parameters, and also reveals detailed information about any assessment results via the "Show more info" button

2.3. Metrics

The Metrics view presents information about metrics stored in the *Orchestrator's* database along with their configuration. When opening the view, the user is presented with information like shown in Figure 5.

For viewing details about a metric's concrete implementation, the user can click the *Show Code* button and is then presented with the information shown in Figure 6.

Configured Metrics

The following metrics are configured in the Cloudfitor orchestrator.

#	Category	Description	Implementation
ActivityLoggingEnabled	Operational security	This metric is used to assess if activity logs are enabled for the cloud service/asset.	Language: LANGUAGE_REGO Show Code
AnomalyDetectionEnabled	Operational security	This metric is used to assess if Anomaly Detection is enabled for the cloud service/asset	Language: LANGUAGE_REGO Show Code

Figure 5. The Metrics view: It shows configured metrics with their name, category, description, and implementation

```

Language: LANGUAGE_REGO

Show Code

package cloudfitor.metrics.activity_logging_enabled

import data.cloudfitor.compare

default applicable = false

default compliant = false

enabled := input.activityLogging.enabled

applicable {
    enabled != null
}

compliant {
    compare(data.operator, data.target_value, enabled)
}
    
```

Figure 6. The view when opening the code of a metric's implementation

2.4. Catalogues

The Catalogues view presents information about catalogues stored in the *Orchestrator*. As MEDINA focuses on the EUCS, this view presents the EUCS catalogue (see Figure 8), and shows details about its categories and controls when opening the catalogue (see Figure 9).

Catalogues

EUCS

EU Cloud Services certification scheme

Figure 7. The overview of a catalogue is shown when opening the Catalogues view

Figure 8. The overview of the EUCS categories

2.5. Certificates

The Certificates view visualizes information about the certificates that have been created via the *Automated Certificate Life Cycle Manager*³.

Figure 9 shows how certificates are displayed in the Certificates view. They include basic information, such as the name, the corresponding cloud service ID, and the certification schema, as well as information about the state history of the certificate.

Figure 9. An example of a certificate as displayed in the Certificates view in the Orchestrator UI

³ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

3. Delivery and usage

3.1. Licensing information

The *Orchestrator* is offered under Apache 2.0 license. The license files and more detailed information can be found in the MEDINA Public GitLab repository⁴.

3.2. Download

The code of the component is available at the public GitLab repository of the MEDINA project: <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/orchestrator>.

3.3. More information

Interested readers can find more information about the Orchestrator at this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225> “D3.6 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures – v3”.

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the *Orchestrator*.

⁴ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/orchestrator>